

PHONOLOGICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF REDUPLICATION

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Annotatsiya: Repetition or reduplication is a main part of linguistics. It is studied not only in stylistics but also in literature as well as in linguistics too. The purpose of this article is to search on the reduplication and its types. Moreover, the article illustrates phonological and morphological aspects of reduplication.

Kalit so'zlar: reduplication, repetition, complete repetition, partial repetition, morphological reduplication, phonological reduplication.

INTRODUCTION

Reduplication can be considered as a word-formation process in which all or part of a word is repeated to convey some form of meaning. A range of patterns are found in terms of both the form and meaning expressed by reduplication, making it one of the most studied phenomena in phonology and morphology.

Reduplication is originated from Latin word having a meaning reduplication or doubling, it is a word in linguistics a repeated word, grammatical form, with repeated use of the initial syllable or root, the whole word a phono-morphological phenomenon consisting of methods of formation. From this point of view, it is partial and complete There are different types of reduplication. In modern Uzbek, this type of word form is plural, continuous and represents grammatical meanings such as repetition. Formed by reduplication units form a lexical-grammatical whole. For example: baland-baland binolar (high-high buildings), dasta-dasta gullar (stacks of flowers), kula-kula (lot of laugh), o'sha-o'sha, katta katta (big-big), etc. these examples illustrate that reduplication emphasizes the meaning of idea by repeating the words. Repetition of any word reduplication does not occur from consecutive occurrences. Reduplication is different in the world is characteristic of many languages in the system, and its task is also diverse. In some literature, the term "reduplication" is considered as "repeated form" or "repeated word" which is used synonymously with the terms.

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Reduplication has been widely used in various works and folklore since ancient times. However, its study as a separate field of linguistics stopped in recent history. Today, Reduplication is a field that has its place and importance in the field of linguistics and literary studies, as well as in stylistics. This area was discussed by Mamajonov A in his manual called "Text linguistics" and in the article "Repetition and its syntactic-stylistic function" (Journal of Uzbek language and literature, 1978.№3 B.60) Hojiahmedov A. "She' in the work "Arts and Classical Rhymes"; in addition, in the works of A. V. Koltsov, N. A.

Nekrasov, A. S. Pushkin and many other poets, the reduplication style was also used

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In linguistics, repetition (reduplication) is the repetition of the same word exactly twice, which also creates different grammatical meanings: multiplicity of the subject, increase of the sign, intensification of the meaning, repetition of the action and long duration, etc. For example, *etak-etak paxta* (means so much cotton) an this is quantitative plural; *ayta-ayta charchamoq* (being tired of telling continuously) is the duration of action. In our language, this method is characterized by complete repetition (*etak-etak paxta*) and partial repetition (*qip-qizil, ko‘m- ko‘k, yam-yashil*) (red, blue, green). And it is occurred in Uzbek language much and it shows repeating in phone. V. Egorov says in one of his articles: “One of the oldest and easiest ways of forming words in many languages of the world is repeated words. Repeating the same word twice, that is, repeated words are related to increasing quality or quantity, speed of movement or repetition is equal.”[1] In many languages, repeated words are even indicators of the plural level of nouns, the degree of improvement of adjectives, the grammatical categories of subtractive numbers, etc.

Reduplication can be considered as a word formation process which makes repetition all or part of a word to convey some form of meaning or to emphasize the meaning. The range of patterns are different from a single segment of being copied to entire phrases. So, the copying occurs on its own, or it can be accompanied by other word formation processes. Moreover, the meanings ranges from iconic meanings, such as repetition to more abstract morpho-syntactic meanings, to quite subtle meanings, difficult to define precisely. Because of this diversity in form and meaning, reduplication has been the subject of a great deal of research, both descriptive and theoretical. Among this diversity, several themes emerge related to accounting for the form of reduplication, which can be loosely categorized in terms of shape, segmental quality, morphological structure, and the repetition mechanism. Any kind of model of reduplication can be able to predict possible patterns and they do not generate unattested patterns.

The installation of lexical repetition in the text raises the level of this work to a higher level. Also, it has an additional effect on the meaning of its termination. In addition, reduplication is widely used in poetry and folklore.

RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

The process of reduplication is closely related to the category of number in nouns, where it is used to increase quantity. For example, if we analyze the sentence "There were rows of fruit trees in the garden", we can understand that there are many fruit trees in the garden. Also, the word row used to reinforce the meaning shows that there is more to the trees and gives the sentence a special mood. Repetition is the repetition of words or phrases, as a result of which the reader (listener) focuses on them, thereby increasing their role in the text. Repetition gives harmony to the artistic text, enhances its emotional impact, it emphasizes the most important ideas. Repetition can be widely used in prose: story and novel. These are often semantic repetitions. For example, in F. M. Dostoyevsky, the image of the bell, which constantly disturbs Raskolnikov's mind throughout the novel, evokes different feelings and thoughts in the reader and serves to deepen the understanding of the work. A.P. Chekhov refers to often repeated characteristic details: the unchanging ritual of receiving guests in the Turkish house ("Ionych"), details of "work" in Belikov's descriptions ("Man at Work"). But the place of repetition is especially important in poetry. Poems are built on the basis of proportional rhythmic quantities - syllables, stress, verses, exact alternation of verses. Rhymes and other sound patterns create sound repetitions. A special type of verbal repetition in poetry is refrain (refrain).

The most common type of reduplication is parallelism. There are different types of repetition -

synonymous, antonymic, through - types of repetition, in particular, parallel constructions. The problem of repetition attracts the attention of many researchers, and the number of works devoted to repetition is constantly growing. Of great interest is the task of distinguishing repetition - on the one hand, an expressive tool and a stylistic tool, and on the other hand, repetition - a type of extension that ensures the structural harmony of the entire text and establishes the hierarchy of its elements. Repetition is a figure of speech that consists of repeating sounds, words, morphemes, synonyms or syntactic constructions in a sufficiently strict sequence. Repetition, like other forms of speech that enhance the expressiveness of a sentence, is the difference between a traditional marker and a situational one. From the point of view, it can be seen as some kind of purposeful deviation from the neutral syntactic norm, for which it is enough to use the word once. There is such a thing as lexical repetition, i.e. repeating a word or phrase in a sentence, paragraph, or entire text. The distance between the repeating units and the number of repetitions can vary, but they should be such that the reader can notice the repetition. According to some resources, there are some types of reduplication which are full and partial reduplication. However, according to some other resources (Travis (2001)[18.1]

On the other hand, other form of reduplication is occurred in linguistics that is morphological and phonological. As mentioned above some parts of speech can be repeated in order to change or to emphasize the meaning of the text. Even suffixes, prefixes or root morphemes also can be repeated. For instance, in Uzbek, “qip-qizil olmalar, yam-yashil maysazor, baland baland tog’lar,” and many others are good examples for morphological reduplication. On the other hand, phonological reduplication is also primitive to have an essential meaning. For instance, “taq-tuq, tiqir-tiqir, bang-bung” and many examples.

CONCLUSION

The role of reduplication in fiction is incomparable. Repetition is used by authors of fiction works to draw the attention of readers to the described events and to exaggerate them. It is used to make it melodious, impressive and attractive. The idea expressed by the artist is reflected in the social-political, philosophical-ethical, educational, nature and scope of problems, the color and variety of lexical repetition used simultaneously with the gloss of artistic symbols. Special attention is also paid to issues such as logical justification, role and importance in revealing the content of the work. Repetition tool shows the ideological maturity, artistic excellence, unique skill of using words of the poet's poetry and the writer's work, and in the artistic work, it enriches its content and gives a special mood to the work.

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